

St. Dominic College of Asia's Bachelor of Arts in Communication employment tracer study

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Abstract

This study discusses the results of the employment tracer study of the Bachelor of Arts in Communication graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia who graduated between 2014 and 2021. The objectives of this tracer study are: to determine the profile of the respondents, length of job search, means of the graduates in finding their first job, and the difficulties they encountered in looking for a job. The study used a quantitative approach wherein 57 out of 80 BA Communication graduates from 2014 to 2021 answered the survey questionnaire given to them. It is revealed that the majority of the graduates took less than three months after graduation to find a job. Moreover, most of them found their first jobs through the internet job search. The graduates had a hard time looking for a job because of their lack of work experience.

Keywords: *St. Dominic College of Asia; Bachelor of Arts in Communication; Employment; Tracer study.*

To cite this article:

Mojica, R. D., & Bautista, M. A. C. (2022). St. Dominic College of Asia's Bachelor of Arts in Communication employment tracer study. *SDCA Journal of Communication and Media Studies*, 3, 14-20.

Introduction

It is the responsibility of institutions engaged in long- and short-term human resource development to monitor the achievement of their graduates in order to assess responsibility and determine if their programs have had an effect on the graduate, the institution, or the country as a whole. One type of empirical study that offers useful data for assessing the outcomes of the education and training provided by a particular higher education institution is the tracer study (Hazaymeh & Dela Peña, 2015).

The data from this tracer research may be used to advance the institution's quality assurance efforts (Schomburg, 2016). A tracer study gives the institution a way to collect information that can further help the improvement of curriculum, output, activities, and programs for current and potential BA Communication students. This can also serve as a basis for how the institution helped the graduates choose their career and their future preferences with regard to the profession.

The importance of education and training being adapted to the present and future demands of societies going through social and economic transformation is one of the core issues with these systems. Education and training must be arranged flexibly within the ever-changing framework rather than according to rigid requirements. It can change and must always be adaptable. To make the greatest use of the limited resources available, it is also necessary to guarantee that the unique conditions of the country in question are considered and taken into account (Schomburg, 2014).

The institution, St. Dominic College of Asia, has been extending its improvement in educational standards to produce globally competitive and efficient graduates. The institution continues to exert effort in providing standard and quality services for the students. This includes upgrading facilities, instruction materials, and services that prepare the students for their profession.

According to Schomburg (2016), graduate and employment surveys are a type of empirical research that can offer important data for assessing the outcomes of the education and training of a particular higher education institution (as cited by Bayed et al., 2021). The information gathered in this study will help the institution evaluate the competency of the graduates. It will also serve as a basis for improvement and other future plans for the said program (Matos & Billones, 2019). In addition, Schomburg (2016) noted that a tracer study, also known as an "alumni survey" or "follow-up survey," should allow the institution of higher education to obtain data on the graduates' professional success (career, status, and income), as well as data on the relevance of their knowledge and skills (relative to their careers and other fields), in order to help identify any potential gaps in a given educational program. Furthermore, tracer studies can be used to establish how university growth will affect the connection between higher education and the labor market (Teichler, 1999, as cited by Gutierrez & Mallari, 2018).

The aim of this research is to track Bachelor of Arts in Communication graduates' performance as a foundation for curricular improvement. It aimed to present the alumni members' demographic and employability profiles, specifically the length of time spent by the graduates for job search, how they found their first job, the difficulties they encountered in looking for a job after graduation, and their current employment profile.

Methodology

A quantitative method was used in this study. From 2014 to 2021, SDCA BA Communication had 80 graduates, but only 57 were able to answer the researcher-made survey questionnaire, which was the main instrument in the study. The study was conducted from October 2021 to February 2022.

Table 1. Respondents of the study according to year graduated

Year Graduated	Total No. of Graduates	Total No. of Respondents
2014	6	3
2015	13	5
2016	16	12
2017	7	6
2018	13	10
2019	16	12
2020	6	6
2021	3	3
Total	80	57

The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents online through Google Forms. They were contacted by the researchers through social media, email, and personal communication. The questionnaire is composed of three parts: their demographic profile, their employment history, and their current employment status.

To analyze the results, the researchers used frequency distribution and percentage to determine the demographic profile, the time it took for the graduates to land a job after graduation, and how they found their first job. In order to determine the difficulties the graduates encountered in applying for a job, the mean was used.

Results and Discussion

The tables below discuss the results of the study based on the data gathered and collected.

Demographic Profile

Table 2. Age of the respondents

Age (years old)	f	%
30 & above	2	3.5
29	2	3.5
28	7	12
27	10	18
26	7	12
25	6	10
24	10	18
23	8	14
22	4	7

Table 2 shows that most of the respondents (10 or 18%) are 27 and 24 years old. This is followed closely by 23 years old with eight (8) respondents (14%). Seven (7) respondents (12%) are 28 and 26 years old, while six (6) respondents (10%) are 25 years old. There are four (4) respondents (7%) that are 22 years old, while two (2) respondents (3.5%) are 29 and 30 years and above respectively. For age 21 and below, there is only one (1) respondent (2%).

Table 3. Gender of the respondents

Gender	f	%
Male	18	32
Female	39	68

This table shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the gender of the respondents. Majority (68%) of the BA Communication graduates are females while the remaining (32%) are males.

Table 4. Civil status of the respondents

Civil Status	f	%
Single	54	95
Married	3	5

This table shows the frequency distribution and percentage of the civil status of the respondents. Majority (95%) of the BA Communication graduates are single while the remaining (5%) are married.

Table 5. Civil status of the respondents

Civil Status	f	%
2014	3	5.26
2015	5	8.77
2016	12	21.05
2017	6	10.53
2018	10	17.54
2019	12	21.05
2020	6	10.53
2021	3	5.26

Most of the respondents of the study graduated in 2016 and 2019. Table 2.4 shows that 12 respondents (21.05%) graduated in 2016 and 2019. There are 10 respondents (17.54%) graduated in 2018. This is followed by graduates from batches 2017 and 2020 with six (6) respondents (10.53%), five (5) respondents (8.77%) who graduated in 2015, while three (3) (5.26%) respondents from batches 2014 and 2021.

Employment History

Table 6. Length of job search

Length of Job Search	f	%
Less than 3 months	32	56
3 – 6 months	10	18
6 months – 1 year	12	21
1 – 2 years	0	0
More than 2 years	2	3
N/A	1	2

Majority of the BA Communication graduates (56%) were hired by their respective employees in just less than three (3) months after graduation. Twelve (12) of them (21%) were hired within six (6) months to one (1) year. While 18% (10 respondents) were hired within three to six months. There are 3% (2 respondents) who were hired more than two years after graduation and only one (1) respondent or 2% is still unemployed.

Table 7. Means of finding the first job

Means of Finding the First Job	f	%
Walk-in application	3	5
Assistance from the school	2	3
Job fair	2	3
Internet job-search sites	22	39
Information from friends	5	9
Recommendation from someone	18	32
Newspaper advertisements	0	0
Job agency assistance	1	2
Others	4	7

Table 7 answers the question “*How did you find your first job?*” It shows that most of the BA Communication graduates (39%) found their jobs through Internet job-search sites such as (but not limited to) Jobstreet.com, LinkedIn, JobsDB, among others. Eighteen (18) of them (32%) landed on their first job through a recommendation from someone. While the remaining said that they found their respective jobs through walk-in applications (5%), information from friends (9%), assistance from the school (3%), job fair (3%) and job agency assistance (2%). The remaining 7% said that their first job were either handling family business or self-employment.

Table 8 shows data on the reasons why the graduates are having a hard time in looking for a job. In the table, most of the BA Communication graduates of SDCA said that they have difficulty of finding a job because they do not have work experience (mean=2.88). Interestingly, lack of opportunities aligned to the field comes second with a mean of 3.27. Lack of training in the field (mean=4.04), salary issues (mean=4.34), strong competition (mean=4.49) and lack of national examinations/ certifications requirements are other reasons.

Table 8. Difficulties in finding a job

Reasons	Mean	Rank
No work experience	2.88	1
Lack of training in the field	4.04	3
Lack of national examination / certification requirements	4.63	6
Lack of strong referrals	5.02	7
Limited opportunities aligned to the field of training	3.27	2
Salary being offered was too low	4.34	4
No jobs available	6.32	8
Strong competition	4.49	5

Current Employment Status**Table 9.** Current employment status

Employment Status	f	%
Employed	57	100
Not Employed	0	0

100% of the respondents are currently employed as shown in Table 9. 57 out of 57 (100%) are employed. None of them are unemployed.

Table 10. Type of sector of the current company

Sector	f	%
Government	2	4
Private	50	87
Non-Government Organization	5	9

Table 10 shows that out of 57 graduates, 50 of them are working in the private sector (87%). Only two (2) respondents are either working on the government (4%) and non-government organizations (5 or 9%).

Table 11. Type of sector of the current company

Sector	f	%
Media and Production	17	29
Creative Arts	2	4
Corporate Communications	1	2
Integrated Marketing Communications	1	2
Advertising	1	2
Public Relations	1	2
Customer Service	20	35
Sales and Marketing	6	10
Education and Training	3	5
Development Communication	3	5
Others	2	4

It is shown in Table 11 that most of the respondents are working in the customer service industry with 20 respondents (35%). Seventeen (17) BA Communication graduates (29%) are working in the media and production industry, while 10% or six (6) graduates are working in the sales and marketing business. There are three (3) respondents each (5%) who work in the fields of education and training, development communication. The following industries have one (1) respondent (2%) each: corporate communications,

advertising, integrated marketing communications and public relations, while two (2) respondents each (4%) who work in the fields of creative arts and others.

Table 12. Relatedness of the current roles to the field of training in college

Sector	f	%
Related	48	84
Not Related	9	16

According to the table above, most of the BA Communication graduates perceived that their training during their stay in SDCA matches their current roles in their respective jobs. 84% (48 respondents) of them agree that their current roles are related to their field of training in college while 16% (9 respondents) said that their field of training is not related at all.

Table 13. Current job position

Sector	f	%
Rank- and- File	41	72
Supervisory Level	15	26
Managerial Level	1	2

Most of the graduates are in the rank- and- file positions making it 41 out of 57 respondents who are currently working (72%). Only 15 of them (26%) are in the supervisory position, and one (1) out of 57 for managerial level. Since the study covers only those who graduated from 2014 up to 2021, it is understandable that most of them are still in the entry-level positions.

Table 14. Current tenure of employment

Sector	f	%
Contractual	45	79
Regular / Permanent	12	21
Temporary / Probationary	0	0

Table 11 discusses the current tenure of employment of the BA Communication graduates of SDCA. There are 45 respondents (79%) who are still a contractual employee and there are 12 (21%) who are already regular or permanent. Considering that the respondents have graduated as early as 2014, they are expected to have passed the six (6)-month probationary period for a regular employment. But the respondents tend to have not passed this. According to Wike and Stokes (2018), unlike the previous generations, millennials and Generation Z workforce are looking for purpose than stability leading them to shift careers from one to other. Since the respondents of the study belong either to the millennial generation or the Generation Z, their employment status reflects the study.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the study, in terms of demographic profile, BA Communication graduates of the St. Dominic College of Asia from 2014 to 2021 are in their twenties, mostly female, and all single. In terms of employment history, SDCA BA Communication graduates are highly employable; they were able to find jobs in less than three months after their respective graduations, mostly through Internet job-search sites, with a lack of work experience as the main hindrance in looking for a job. In terms of current employment status, the graduates of SDCA under the BA Communication program are currently employed in the private sector as a rank-and-file employee under a customer service company that has a related training experience for them during their stay at the University of Perpetual Help System Delta (UPHSD) in Calamba, Laguna.

This study recommends that there should be another and more extensive tracer study to conduct using a more comprehensive data gathering approach that covers more respondents, such as curriculum and instruction. Moreover, the results of this study can be considered to improve the curriculum and instruction of the program. The data can also be utilized in planning for the university and the program.

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